

SIEVE OF ERATOSTHENES AND WHEEL FACTORIZATION

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Abstract

This paper presents a refinement of the Sieve method of Eratosthenes in conjunction with wheel factorization. The result is to use less memory.

Sieve Wheel or Modular Sieve

With the sieve of Eratosthenes^[1] algorithm in the Boolean vector *SIEVE* of size n initially all set to *true* all elements associated with multiples of primes p can be set to *false* using this pseudocode:

```
for (p = 2; p < sqrt(n); p++)
  if ( SIEVE[p] )
    for (m = p * p; m < n; m += p)
      SIEVE[m] = false;
```

An improvement can be made by using the Wheel factorization^[2] or equivalently by the use of modular arithmetic^[3].

Given an integer $m \geq 1$, called modulus, two integers p and q are congruent modulo m $p \equiv q \pmod{m}$ if m is a divisor of their difference $p - q$. As we will see, the modulus m corresponds to the size of the wheel which we will indicate with $bW = m$, furthermore we will indicate the operator modulo $q \pmod{m}$ also with $q \% m$.

We therefore consider the modulo operator $p \pmod{bW}$ which denotes the unique integer r such that $0 \leq r < bW$ and $r \equiv p \pmod{bW}$ then $p = r + k \cdot bW$ where r is the remainder of p when divided by bW .

In modular arithmetic the set of integers $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, bW - 1\}$ is called the least residue system modulo bW so let's take a specific one residue system modulo bW set of $\varphi(bW)$ integers, where $\varphi(bW)$ is Euler's totient function^[4], that are relatively prime to bW and mutually incongruent under modulus bW , called a reduced residue system modulo bW .

To make a sieve wheel for the purpose to find prime numbers less than n we choose $bW < \sqrt{n}$ and bW divisible by a set of prime numbers $\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\}$ then we choose an appropriate reduced residue system modulo bW stored in the vector *RW* of length $nR = \varphi(bW)$.

In this way we only store the numbers belonging to the congruence class or residue in *RW* and therefore multiples of $\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\}$ are automatically excluded.

Example $bW = 6$

for $p = -1 + 6 \cdot k$

in the row 0 corresponding to the remainder -1 : $s = 1$ $r = -1$ $r \cdot s = -1$ $m_{min} = 6 \cdot k \cdot k$

in the row 1 corresponding to the remainder 1 : $s = -1$ $r = -1$ $r \cdot s = 1$ $m_{min} = 6 \cdot k \cdot k - 2 \cdot k$

for $p = 1 + 6 \cdot k$

in the row 0 corresponding to the remainder -1 : $s = -1$ $r = 1$ $r \cdot s = -1$ $m_{min} = 6 \cdot k \cdot k$

in the row 1 corresponding to the remainder 1 : $s = 1$ $r = 1$ $r \cdot s = 1$ $m_{min} = 6 \cdot k \cdot k + 2 \cdot k$

Then in the Boolean array *SIEVE* of size $2 \cdot (n/6 + 1)$ initially all set to *true* and elements associated with multiples of primes $-1 + 6 \cdot k$ and $1 + 6 \cdot k$ can be set to *false* using this pseudocode:

```
for (k=1; k<=sqrt(n)/6; k++){
  if (SIEVE[0,k]){
    for (m=6*k*k; m<n/6+1; m+=-1+6*k)
      SIEVE[0,m]=false;
    for (m=6*k*k-2*k; m<n/6+1; m+=-1+6*k)
      SIEVE[1,m]=false;}
  if (SIEVE[1,k]){
    for (m=6*k*k; m<n/6+1; m+=1+6*k)
      SIEVE[0,m]=false;
    for (m=6*k*k+2*k; m<n/6+1; m+=1+6*k)
      SIEVE[1,m]=false;}
}
```

In general if $p = RW[j] + bW \cdot k$ (for convenience we consider $RW[j] \leq 1$ and $k > 0$) and if $s = RW[x]$ we have:

$$\begin{aligned} (RW[x] + bW \cdot k) \cdot (RW[j] + bW \cdot k) &= (RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) + bW \cdot (bW \cdot k \cdot k + k \cdot RW[x] + k \cdot RW[j]) = \\ &= (RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) \% bW + bW \cdot (bW \cdot k \cdot k + k \cdot RW[x] + k \cdot RW[j] + \lfloor (RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) / bW \rfloor) \end{aligned}$$

and $m_{min} = bW \cdot k \cdot k + k \cdot (RW[x] + RW[j]) + \lfloor (RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) / bW \rfloor$

or if $(RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) \% bW > 1$ adding and subtracting bW becomes

$$m_{min} = bW \cdot k \cdot k + k \cdot (RW[x] + RW[j]) + \lfloor (RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) / bW \rfloor + 1$$

we build two array of size $nR * nR$ for the coefficients C_1 and C_2 then for each $RW[i]$

and for each $RW[j]$ finding $RW[x]$ such that $(RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) \% bW = RW[i]$

then if $(RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) \% bW = RW[i]$ we have $C_1[i, j] = RW[x] + RW[j]$

and if $RW[i] = 1$ or $RW[j] = 1$ or $RW[i] = RW[j]$ then $C_2[i, j] = \lfloor (RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) / bW \rfloor$

otherwise $C_2[i, j] = 1 + \lfloor (RW[x] \cdot RW[j]) / bW \rfloor$

In the row corresponding to the residue $RW[i]$ if $p = RW[j] + bW \cdot k$ then

$$m_{min} = bW \cdot k \cdot k + k \cdot C_1[i, j] + C_2[i, j]$$

Example $bW = 30$

$nR=8$ and $RW=[-23, -19, -17, -13, -11, -7, -1, 1]$

$C1=$

-22, -32, -28, -32, -28, -8, -8, -22
-30, -18, -30, -30, -12, -30, -12, -18
-34, -26, -16, -14, -34, -26, -14, -16
-42, -42, -18, -12, -18, -18, -18, -12
-46, -20, -34, -26, -10, -14, -20, -10
-24, -36, -36, -24, -24, -6, -24, -6
-36, -30, -24, -36, -30, -24, 0, 0
-40, -38, -40, -20, -22, -20, -2, 2

$C2=$

0, 9, 7, 9, 7, 1, 1, 0
6, 0, 8, 8, 1, 6, 1, 0
9, 5, 0, 1, 9, 5, 1, 0
15, 15, 1, 0, 3, 3, 1, 0
18, 1, 10, 6, 0, 2, 1, 0
1, 11, 11, 5, 5, 0, 1, 0
10, 7, 4, 10, 7, 4, 0, 0
13, 12, 13, 3, 4, 3, 0, 0

In the Boolean array *SIEVE* of size $nR * \lceil n/bW \rceil$ initially all set to *true* all elements associated with multiples of primes $p=RW[j]+bW \cdot k$ can be set to *false* using this pseudocode:

```
for (k = 1; k <= sqrt(n) / bW; k++)
  for (j = 0; j < nR ; j++)
    if( SIEVE[ j, k ] )
      for (i = 0; i < nR ; i++)
        for (m = bW * k * k + k * C1[ i, j ] + C2[ i, j ]; m < n / bW + 1; m += RW[ j ] + bW * k)
          SIEVE[ i, m ] = false;
```

An improvement obtained is to have numbers smaller than n/bW and the use of a memory equal to $\varphi(bW) \cdot n / bW$.

In addition the possibility of making a segmented version using a bit space $\varphi(bW) \cdot \sqrt{n} / bW$, an example is shown below with the possible choice of the value of the wheel modulus.

Other sieves generally use \sqrt{n} as memory for segmentation instead this wheel sieve uses the product of the prime numbers following the basis $\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\}$ with $p_1=2$ and $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_s$ so that a pre-sieving can be done, in this way the memory used is slightly higher than $\varphi(bW) \cdot \sqrt{n} / bW$ but is always less than \sqrt{n} .

Segmented bit Wheel Sieve

Below is shown the C++ code of a segmented bit wheel sieve with adjustable modulus:

```
/// This is an implementation of the bit wheel segmented sieve
/// with max modulus wheel choice 30, 210, 2310
#include <iostream>
#include <cmath>
#include <algorithm>
#include <vector>
#include <cstdlib>
#include <stdint.h>
#include <chrono>

const int64_t PrimesBase[6] = {2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13};
const int64_t n_PB_max = 5;

const int64_t del_bit[8] =
{
    ~(1 << 0), ~(1 << 1), ~(1 << 2), ~(1 << 3), ~(1 << 4), ~(1 << 5), ~(1 << 6), ~(1 << 7)
};

const int64_t bit_count[256] =
{
    0, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 2, 3, 1, 2, 2, 3, 2, 3, 3, 4, 1, 2, 2, 3, 2, 3, 3, 4, 2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5,
    1, 2, 2, 3, 2, 3, 3, 4, 2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6,
    1, 2, 2, 3, 2, 3, 3, 4, 2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6,
    2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6, 4, 5, 5, 6, 5, 6, 6, 7,
    1, 2, 2, 3, 2, 3, 3, 4, 2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6,
    2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6, 4, 5, 5, 6, 5, 6, 6, 7,
    2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 4, 4, 5, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6, 3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6, 4, 5, 5, 6, 5, 6, 6, 7,
    3, 4, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 6, 4, 5, 5, 6, 5, 6, 6, 7, 4, 5, 5, 6, 5, 6, 6, 7, 5, 6, 6, 7, 6, 7, 7, 8
};

int64_t Euclidean_Diophantine( int64_t coeff_a, int64_t coeff_b)
{
    // return y in Diophantine equation coeff_a x + coeff_b y = 1
    int64_t k=1;
    std::vector<int64_t> div_t;
    std::vector<int64_t> rem_t;
    std::vector<int64_t> coeff_t;
    div_t.push_back(coeff_a);
```

```

rem_t.push_back(coeff_b);
coeff_t.push_back((int64_t)0);
div_t.push_back((int64_t)div_t[0]/rem_t[0]);
rem_t.push_back((int64_t)div_t[0]%rem_t[0]);
coeff_t.push_back((int64_t)0);
while (rem_t[k] > 1)
{
    k++;
    div_t.push_back((int64_t)rem_t[k-2]/rem_t[k-1]);
    rem_t.push_back((int64_t)rem_t[k-2]%rem_t[k-1]);
    coeff_t.push_back((int64_t)0);
}
k--;
coeff_t[k] = -div_t[k+1];
if (k > 0)
    coeff_t[k-1] = (int64_t)1;
while (k > 1)
{
    k--;
    coeff_t[k-1]=coeff_t[k+1];
    coeff_t[k] += (int64_t)(coeff_t[k+1]*(-div_t[k+1]));
}
if (k == 1)
    return (int64_t)(coeff_t[k-1] + coeff_t[k] * (-div_t[k]));
else
    return (int64_t)(coeff_t[0]);
}

```

```

int64_t segmented_bit_sieve_wheel(uint64_t n, int64_t max_bW)
{
    int64_t sqrt_n = (int64_t) std::sqrt(n);
    int64_t count_p = (int64_t)0;
    int64_t n_PB = (int64_t)3;
    int64_t bW = (int64_t)30;
    //get bW modulus equal to p1*p2*...*pn <=max_bW with n=n_PB
    while(n_PB < n_PB_max && (bW * PrimesBase[n_PB] <= std::min(max_bW, sqrt_n)))
    {
        bW *= PrimesBase[n_PB];
        n_PB++;
    }
    for (int64_t i = 0; i < n_PB; i++)

```

```

if (n > PrimesBase[i])
    count_p++;

if (n > 1 + PrimesBase[n_PB - 1]){
    int64_t k_end = (n < bW) ? (int64_t)2 : (int64_t) (n / (uint64_t)bW + 1);
    int64_t k_sqrt = (int64_t) std::sqrt(k_end / bW) + 1;

    //find reduced residue system modulo bW
    std::vector<char> Remainder_t(bW, true);
    for (int64_t i = 0; i < n_PB; i++)
        for (int64_t j = PrimesBase[i]; j < bW; j += PrimesBase[i])
            Remainder_t[j] = false;
    std::vector<int64_t> RW;
    for (int64_t j = 2; j < bW; j++)
        if (Remainder_t[j]==true)
            RW.push_back(-bW+j);
    RW.push_back(1);
    int64_t nR = RW.size(); // nR=phi(bW)
    std::vector<int64_t> C1(nR * nR);
    std::vector<int64_t> C2(nR * nR);
    for (int64_t j = 0; j < nR-2; j++)
    {
        int64_t rW_t, rW_t1;
        rW_t1=Euclidean_Diophantine(bW, -RW[j]);
        for (int64_t i = 0; i < nR; i++)
        {
            if (i == j)
            {
                C2[nR * i + j]=0;
                C1[nR * i + j] = RW[j] + 1;
            }
            else if(i == nR-3-j )
            {
                C2[nR * i + j] = 1;
                C1[nR * i + j] = RW[j] - 1;
            }
            else
            {
                rW_t = (int64_t)(rW_t1 * (-RW[i])) % bW;
                if (rW_t > 1)
                    rW_t -= bW;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

    C1[nR * i + j] = rW_t + RW[j];
    C2[nR * i + j] = (int64_t)(rW_t * RW[j]) / bW + 1;
    if (i == nR - 1)
        C2[nR * i + j] -= 1;
    }
}
C2[nR * j + nR-2] = (int64_t)1;
C1[nR * j + nR-2] = -(bW + RW[j]) - 1;
C1[nR * j + nR-1] = RW[j] + 1;
C2[nR * j + nR-1] = (int64_t)0;
}
for (int64_t i = nR-2; i < nR; i++)
{
    C2[nR*i+nR-2] = (int64_t)0;
    C1[nR*i+nR-2] = -RW[i]-1;
    C1[nR*i+nR-1] = RW[i]+1;
    C2[nR*i+nR-1] = (int64_t)0;
}
int64_t nB = nR / 8;
int64_t segment_size = 1;
int64_t p_mask_i = (int64_t)4;
for (int64_t i = 0; i < p_mask_i; i++)
    segment_size *= (bW + RW[i]); // if bW=30 = 7*11*13*17
while (segment_size < k_sqrt && p_mask_i < 7)
{
    segment_size *= (bW + RW[p_mask_i]); // if bW=30 max value = 7*11*13*17*19*23*29
    p_mask_i++;
}

int64_t segment_size_b = nB * segment_size;
std::vector<uint8_t> Primes(nB + segment_size_b, 0xff);
std::vector<uint8_t> Segment_i(nB + segment_size_b, 0xff);
int64_t pb, mb, mmin, ib, i, jb, j, k, kb;
int64_t kmax = (int64_t) std::sqrt(segment_size / bW) + (int64_t)1;
for (k = (int64_t)1; k <= kmax; k++)
{
    kb = k * nB;
    for (jb = 0; jb < nB; jb++)
    {
        for (j = 0; j < 8; j++)
        {

```



```

kmax=(std::min(segment_size,(int64_t)std::sqrt((k_low+segment_size)/bW)+2));
j=p_mask_i;
for(k=(int64_t)1; k<=kmax; k++)
{
    kb=k*nB;
    for (jb = 0; jb<nB; jb++)
    {
        for (; j < 8; j++)
        {
            if (Primes[kb+jb]& (1 << j))
            {
                for (ib = 0; ib<nB; ib++)
                {
                    for (i = 0; i < 8; i++)
                    {
                        pb=bW*k+RW[j+jb*8];
                        mmin=-k_low+bW*k*k+ k*C1[(i+ib*8)*nR+j+jb*8] + C2[(i+ib*8)*nR+j+jb*8];
                        if (mmin<0)
                            mmin=(mmin%pb+pb)%pb;
                        mmin*=nB;
                        pb*=nB;
                        for (mb =mmin; mb <= segment_size_b; mb += pb)
                            Segment_t[mb+ib] &= del_bit[i];
                    }
                }
            }
        }
        j=(int64_t)0;
    }
}
for ( kb =nB+kb_low; kb <std::min (kb_low+segment_size_b+nB,nB*k_end); kb++)
    count_p+=bit_count[Segment_t[kb-kb_low]];
}
if (kb==nB*k_end && kb-kb_low<=segment_size_b && kb-kb_low>(int64_t)0)
    for (ib = 0; ib<nB; ib++)
        for (i = 0; i < 8; i++)
            if (Segment_t[kb-kb_low+ib]& (1 << i) && RW[i+ib*8]<(int64_t)(n%bW-bW))
                count_p++;
}
}
return count_p;

```

```
}
```

```
int main()
```

```
{
```

```
    int64_t count_p;
```

```
    auto ti = std::chrono::system_clock::now();
```

```
    // segmented_bit_sieve_wheel(n, max_bW) with max_bW= 30 , 210 , 2310 for set modulus
```

```
    count_p = segmented_bit_sieve_wheel(1000000000, 210);
```

```
    auto tf = std::chrono::system_clock::now();
```

```
    std::cout << count_p << " prime numbers found " << std::endl;
```

```
    std::chrono::duration<double> delta_temp = tf - ti;
```

```
    std::cout << " \n" << "t: " << delta_temp.count() << " s" << std::endl;
```

```
    return 0;
```

```
}
```

bit Wheel Sieve size 6

```
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <math.h>
#include <vector>
#include <iostream>
#include <stdint.h>
#include <chrono>

typedef uint64_t word_type;
int word_exp = 6;
int word_m1 = (1 << word_exp) - 1;

unsigned long long int sieve_prime_wheel_6(unsigned long long int n)
{
    unsigned long long int count_p = (n < 3ull) ? 0 : (n < 4ull) ? 1 : (n < 6ull) ? 2 : (n < 8ull) ? 3 : (n <= 10ull) ? 4 : 2;
    if (n > 10ull){
        unsigned long long int kmax = n / 6;
        unsigned long long int dim_vec = ((kmax + word_m1) >> word_exp);
        std::vector<word_type> Prime5mod6(dim_vec, 0ull);
        std::vector<word_type> Prime1mod6(dim_vec, 0ull);
        Prime5mod6[0] |= 1;
        Prime1mod6[0] |= 1;
        if((kmax & word_m1) > 0){
            for(unsigned long long int kb = (kmax & word_m1) + 1; kb <= word_m1; kb++){
                Prime5mod6[dim_vec - 1] |= (1ull << kb);
                Prime1mod6[dim_vec - 1] |= (1ull << kb);
            }
        }
        unsigned long long int m, ksqr;
        ksqr = (unsigned long long int)std::sqrt(kmax) + 1;
        for(unsigned long long int k = 1; k <= ksqr; k++){
            if((Prime5mod6[k >> word_exp] & (1ull << (k & word_m1))) == 0){
                for(m = 6 * k * k; m <= kmax; m += (6 * k - 1)){
                    Prime5mod6[m >> word_exp] |= 1ull << (m & word_m1);
                    Prime1mod6[(m - 2 * k) >> word_exp] |= 1ull << ((m - 2 * k) & word_m1);
                }
                m -= 2 * k;
                for(; m <= kmax; m += (6 * k - 1)){
                    Prime1mod6[m >> word_exp] |= 1ull << (m & word_m1);
                }
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```

    }
}
if((Prime1mod6[k >> word_exp] & (1ull << (k & word_m1))) == 0){
    for(m = 6 * k * k; m + 2 * k <= kmax; m += (6 * k + 1)){
        Prime5mod6[m >> word_exp] |= 1ull << (m & word_m1);
        Prime1mod6[(m + 2 * k) >> word_exp] |= 1ull << ((m + 2 * k) & word_m1);
    }
    for(; m <= kmax; m += (6 * k + 1)){
        Prime5mod6[m >> word_exp] |= 1ull << (m & word_m1);
    }
}
}
for(unsigned long long int k = 1; k <= kmax; k++){
    if(((Prime5mod6[k >> word_exp] & (1ull << (k & word_m1))) == 0))
        count_p++;
    if(((Prime1mod6[k >> word_exp] & (1ull << (k & word_m1))) == 0))
        count_p++;
}
if(((Prime1mod6[kmax >> word_exp] & (1ull << (kmax & word_m1))) == 0) && n % 6 <= 1)
    count_p--;
}
return count_p;
}

int main()
{
    unsigned long long int n = 1000000000;

    auto ti = std::chrono::system_clock::now();
    std::cout << " found " << sieve_prime_wheel_6(n) << " primes < " << n << std::endl;
    auto tf = std::chrono::system_clock::now();

    std::chrono::duration<double> delta_temp = tf - ti;
    std::cout << " \n" << "t: " << delta_temp.count() << " s" << std::endl;

    return 0;
}

```

References

[1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sieve_of_Eratosthenes

[2] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wheel_factorization

[3] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Modular_arithmetic

[4] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Euler%27s_totient_function